

HydroCAD

Prepared by Complete Design INC.

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Type II 24-hr 100-Year Rainfall=2.50"

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Time span=0.00-48.00 hrs, dt=0.04 hrs, 1201 points
Runoff by SBUH method, Split Pervious/Imperv.
Reach routing by Stor-Ind method - Pond routing by Stor-Ind method

Subcatchment A1: TRIBUTARY

Runoff Area=8,382 sf 100.00% Impervious Runoff Depth=2.27"
Tc=10.0 min CN=0/98 Runoff=0.48 cfs 0.036 af

Pond T1: INFILTRATION TRENCH

Peak Elev=3.88' Storage=559 cf Inflow=0.48 cfs 0.036 af
Outflow=0.07 cfs 0.036 af

Total Runoff Area = 0.192 ac Runoff Volume = 0.036 af Average Runoff Depth = 2.27"
0.00% Pervious = 0.000 ac 100.00% Impervious = 0.192 ac

Summary for Subcatchment A1: TRIBUTARY

Runoff = 0.48 cfs @ 11.97 hrs, Volume= 0.036 af, Depth= 2.27"

Runoff by SBUH method, Split Pervious/Imperv., Time Span= 0.00-48.00 hrs, dt= 0.04 hrs
 Type II 24-hr 100-Year Rainfall=2.50"

Area (sf)	CN	Description
6,291	98	Paved parking, HSG A
374	98	Unconnected roofs, HSG A
1,717	98	Unconnected roofs, HSG A
8,382	98	Weighted Average
8,382	98	100.00% Impervious Area

Tc (min)	Length (feet)	Slope (ft/ft)	Velocity (ft/sec)	Capacity (cfs)	Description
10.0					Direct Entry,

Subcatchment A1: TRIBUTARY

Hydrograph

Summary for Pond T1: INFILTRATION TRENCH

Inflow Area = 0.192 ac, 100.00% Impervious, Inflow Depth = 2.27" for 100-Year event
 Inflow = 0.48 cfs @ 11.97 hrs, Volume= 0.036 af
 Outflow = 0.07 cfs @ 12.55 hrs, Volume= 0.036 af, Atten= 85%, Lag= 34.9 min
 Discarded = 0.07 cfs @ 12.55 hrs, Volume= 0.036 af

Routing by Stor-Ind method, Time Span= 0.00-48.00 hrs, dt= 0.04 hrs
 Peak Elev= 3.88' @ 12.55 hrs Surf.Area= 480 sf Storage= 559 cf

Plug-Flow detention time= 59.6 min calculated for 0.036 af (100% of inflow)
 Center-of-Mass det. time= 59.6 min (823.4 - 763.8)

Volume	Invert	Avail.Storage	Storage Description
#1	0.00'	576 cf	15.00'W x 32.00'L x 4.00'H Prismatic 1,920 cf Overall x 30.0% Voids

Device	Routing	Invert	Outlet Devices
#1	Discarded	0.00'	3.600 in/hr Exfiltration over Wetted area

Discarded OutFlow Max=0.07 cfs @ 12.55 hrs HW=3.88' (Free Discharge)
 ↳ 1=Exfiltration (Exfiltration Controls 0.07 cfs)

Pond T1: INFILTRATION TRENCH

